

Probiotic hemp milk-market growth: An updated review

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Abstract

Live bacteria and yeasts are known as probiotics, and they may be good for one's health. Probiotics are living microorganisms that provide health benefits to their hosts, potentially aiding in the treatment or prevention of various diseases, including diarrhea, irritable bowel syndrome, ulcerative colitis, and Crohn's disease. Industrial *Cannabis sativa*, (hemp or fiber type) milk is made by blending hemp seeds with water and then straining the mixture to create a creamy, smooth milk alternative. It is among the best plant milks to balance with an assortment of benefits spanning from being a good source of omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids, and necessary amino acids, to minerals including magnesium, iron, and calcium. The global Hemp Milk industry is estimated to be worth USD 135.3 million by 2025. It is anticipated to reach USD 242.3 million by 2035, reflecting a CAGR of 6.0% over the assessment period 2025 to 2035. The hemp milk market is a niche but rapidly expanding segment of the global plant-based milk market. Hemp milk, with its unique profile of essential fatty acids, protein, and antioxidants, is perfectly positioned to meet these demands. The global hemp milk market is very competitive, with both established brands and new entrants. Companies prioritize product quality, affordability, and creative formulae, particularly in packaging and flavor diversity. Consumer preference for healthier and sustainable foods has been one of the most significant drivers in the growth of the hemp milk market.

Keywords: *Bifidobacterium infantis*; Industrial *Cannabis sativa*; Probiotic; Plant based milk; Hemp milk; India

1. Introduction

Plant-based milk industry has been enlarged with increasing demand for plant milk types and their products. Plant-based milk is one of the most popular vegan products due to various factors and perspectives [10- 79]. The factors are health issues, plant-based milk contains no lactose sugar, making it a favored alternative for customers with lactose intolerance, and it is free of animal hormones and cholesterol. Moreover, recent studies have established the significant role of plant-based milk in improving or enhancing the immune system, having potential antimicrobial effects, lowering the risk of cardiovascular and gastrointestinal diseases, lowering the risk of low bone mass, and having extremely high antioxidant levels with free radical scavenging properties [12-50]. According to raw material, plant-based vegetable milk types can be divided into five categories as cereal-based (oat, rice, corn and spelt milks), legume-based (soy, peanut, lupine and cowpea milks), nut-based (almond, coconut, hazelnut, pistachio, walnut and cashew milks), seed-based (sesame, flax, hemp and sun flower) [10- 79].

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Live bacteria and yeasts are known as probiotics, and they may be good for one's health [10- 25, 80, 81]. Probiotics are living microorganisms that provide health benefits to their hosts, potentially aiding in the treatment or prevention of various diseases, including diarrhea, irritable bowel syndrome, ulcerative colitis, and Crohn's disease [10- 79-81]. They can be found in some meals and supplements as well as in the human digestive system [10- 35]. Probiotic bacteria are beneficial. They are found all over the body, although most people only think of the stomach and intestines when they think of them [10- 45-81]. Fermented foods such as yogurts and kimchi are sources of probiotics. Numerous studies proved lactic acid bacteria (LAB), *bifidobacteria*, and *Bifidobacterium infantis*, *B. longum*, *B. lactis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *S. boulardii*, *S. lactis*, etc. could be used as probiotics [10- 55-81]. Additionally, probiotic supplements are also available. Probiotics are foods and/or supplements that contain non-pathogenic microbes such as bacteria and yeast that colonize the gut and can potentially yield a variety of health benefits [10- 55]. Research into the various ways in which probiotic bacteria could be used in the treatment of intestinal disorders is ongoing. Therefore clinical studies and laboratory experiments, have been conducted in order to know how probiotics affect gut microbiome disorders [10- 55-81]. Studies can prove that probiotics can alleviate a variety of gastrointestinal ailments and improve overall health [10- 79]. The ability of probiotics to modify the immunological response of the host, antagonize pathogenic microbes, or compete for adhesion sites with pathogenic microorganisms is related to the action of probiotics against microorganisms [10- 65-79]. Infections of the digestive tract, irritable bowel, lactose intolerance, allergies, infections of the urogenital tract, cystic fibrosis, and various cancers can all be prevented and treated with the use of probiotics. They can reduce the side effects of various antibiotics [10- 50-79]. Certain bacteria, known as probiotics, have had a vastly beneficial effect on people's health; considering their benefits they have been mixed with a wide variety of foods for several decades now. In the field of oral health, dental caries, periodontal disease, and bad breath can be prevented and treated with the use of probiotics [10- 65-79]. The findings of several of these clinical studies indicate that probiotics may be beneficial in the treatment and prevention of various diseases and health issues [10- 25, 80, 81].

Cannabis sativa has been used for thousands of years for recreational, medicinal, or religious purposes [1-9, 82-123]. Now a days *Cannabis sativa* has been domesticated, cultivated and distributed throughout the world. *Cannabis sativa* is a flowering plant from the *Cannabaceae* family and genus *Cannabis*. *Cannabis sativa* L., is classified into two types as Industrial *Cannabis sativa*, (hemp or fiber type) and Medical *Cannabis sativa* L.(drug or marijuana) based on its THC content [1-9, 82-123]. Medical *Cannabis sativa* (drug or marijuana) contains a very high levels of THC (above 0.3 to 38% of dry weight) [1-52, 82-123]. On the other hand Industrial *Cannabis sativa*, (hemp or fiber type) contains very low levels of THC (0 to 0.3% of dry weight) [1-9, 82-123]. Industrial *Cannabis sativa*, (hemp or fiber type) milk is made by blending hemp seeds with water and then straining the mixture to create a creamy, smooth milk alternative [1-9]. It is among the best plant milks to balance with an assortment of benefits spanning from being a good source of omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids, and necessary amino acids, to minerals including magnesium, iron, and calcium [1-9, 82-123]. Among the prime reasons why hemp milk has been gaining momentum is due to its positive nutritional balance [1-9]. Unlike other seed milks such as almond or soy milk, hemp milk contains all nine of the essential amino acids and is, therefore a complete vegetarian and vegan protein source for people with dietary needs [1-9, 82-123]. Hemp seed milk is one of the seed-based milks and it has high nutrition values because it is composed of lipids (1.25-5.00%), proteins (0.83-4.00%), carbohydrates (2.5-20.0%), vitamin E, minerals (sodium, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, calcium, sulfur, iron, and zinc) and all essential amino acids with high in polyunsaturated fatty acids (linolenic acid and linoleic acid) [1-9-78]. Due to the current dynamic development of sciences related to food and human nutrition, a correlation has been confirmed between the health status and nutritional patterns. A well-balanced diet is the key factor in diseases prevention and treatment [1-9-78]. The growing nutritional interests and awareness of consumers have prompted many producers to manufacture functional food [1-9-78].

2. Probiotic Hemp Milk: Market Size

The global Hemp Milk industry is estimated to be worth USD 135.3 million by 2025. It is anticipated to reach USD 242.3 million by 2035, reflecting a CAGR of 6.0% over the assessment period 2025 to 2035 [53-77]. The hemp milk market is a niche but rapidly expanding segment of the global plant-based milk market [77]. Hemp milk, with its unique profile of essential fatty acids, protein, and antioxidants, is perfectly positioned to meet these demands. By adding hemp milk to functional drinks, business entities can offer a product portfolio that not only is a dairy-free substitute but also helps to advance consumer wellness objectives [53- 77]. The impact on the market will be significant as customers continue to seek more holistic solutions to wellness, thus propelling the demand for hemp milk as an ingredient for health-enhancing beverages. The production of protein powders from hemp milk is one of the most thrilling developments in the hemp milk industry [53- 77]. While plant-based protein powders made from peas, rice, and soy have been around for a long time, hemp-based protein powder is increasingly becoming popular due to its nutritional benefits and digestibility. These powders are being sold as a more digestible and complete protein source than other plant-based alternatives, and thus especially attractive to vegans, athletes, and consumers seeking non-dairy protein

supplements[53- 77]. Hemp milk, which is high in essential amino acids and omega fatty acids, is the perfect foundation upon which to build these powders [53-77]. Demand is based on some factors such as vegan consumption, nutritional content, carbon emissions, lactose intolerance, and other factors.

The global hemp milk market is very competitive, with both established brands and new entrants. Companies prioritize product quality, affordability, and creative formulae, particularly in packaging and flavor diversity. As consumer preferences shift, there is a greater emphasis on developing unique flavor profiles, convenient serving sizes, and accessible formats[53- 77]. Some of the Leading Brands: Hemp Foods Australia, JOI, Good Hemp, Pacific Foods, Nutiva, Living Harvest, Elixinol, Hemp Milk Company, Seventh Generation, The Hemp Company, Oatly, Planet Hemp, REBBL, and Vitasoy. With continued demand growth in different regions, especially in new markets, competition is increasingly getting more intense. Further, companies are making investments in locking in supply chains and building distribution networks to guarantee constant availability of products, thus adding fuel to the market's dynamic and competitive nature [53- 77].

The global increase in protein consumption, fuelled by increased interest in body-building, muscle growth, weight loss, and overall wellness, is driving demand for hemp protein powders [53- 77]. Hemp milk's popularity as a foundation for protein supplements stems from its natural and balanced nutritional profile [53- 77]. The use of hemp milk as a non-dairy creamer is also supported by the fact that it can be used for most coffees, from lattes and cappuccinos to iced coffees. Hemp milk is perfect for coffee brewers who use vegetable-based coffee because it can create smooth, frothy textures to hot or iced beverages [53- 77]. Along with other vegetable milks, hemp milk is already starting to appear on the menus of coffee houses because specialty and high-end coffee shops are demanding it [53- 77]. Consumers are increasingly seeking protein products that do not contain the negative side effects historically associated with animal proteins or overly processed protein powders [53- 77]. Hemp milk protein powders are considered a natural clean choice [53- 77]. Consumer preference for healthier and sustainable foods has been one of the most significant drivers in the growth of the hemp milk market[53- 77]. Individuals are becoming more aware of the effect they have on the planet, and hemp as a crop is seen as one of the most sustainable [53- 77]. Hemp requires less water to cultivate than other plant-based foods eaten as such, i.e., almonds or oats, and does not need herbicides and pesticides sprayed[53- 77]. With increasing sustainability as a key driver of buying habits, hemp milk is taking advantage of this green tide. Rising demand for plant-based diets like veganism, flexitarianism, and dairy-free diets also propagated demand for alternative milks [53- 79].

There were only a handful of studies on the knowledge and consumption of probiotics and prebiotics among Indians, mainly conducted in urban areas and middle to high-income households [50- 70-79]. Limited research showed that the knowledge of probiotics had increased appreciably in the past decade, while there is still poor technical knowledge among Indians [50- 70-77]. Simultaneously, prebiotics is an unfamiliar concept to the general public. Younger individuals are more aware than their older counterparts [50- 70-77]. The probiotics market in India offers several milk-based beverages, yogurt, and curd, while few non-dairy beverages are available from overseas. The prebiotics market in India has several powder formulas and some chewable tablets [50- 70-77]. The consumption of probiotics and prebiotics is limited to popular foods like curd, probiotic drinks, buttermilk, and milk, wheat, onion, tomatoes respectively[50- 70-77]. The modern Indian diet lacks traditional probiotic and prebiotic sources despite their presence in several regional cuisines [50- 70-77]. Furthermore, awareness of these foods and the knowledge and belief in their health benefits are the most influential factors in their consumption [50- 70-77]. Contrarily, the perception of not requiring these foods for the maintenance of good health prevents their consumption [50- 70-77]. Improving awareness and knowledge while offering diverse gut-healthy foods in all strata of Indian society can increase the utilization of these foods and improve general health and prevent chronic diseases [12-53-78].

Today, the increasing demand for plant-based milk expands the product variety and market size [12-53-78]. The demand for the plant-based milk market was expected to reach a value of US\$ 13.24 billion in 2021 and is expected to reach an overall market value of US\$ 30.79 billion by 2031 [50-78]. Concerns regarding the use of animal products have also spurred ethical discussions. In terms of environmental concerns, it has been determined that the carbon emissions produced by the production of plant-based milk are significantly lower than those created by dairy milk production [53-78].

There are certain classical examples where the consumers are being regularly cheated due to lack of awareness, including the difference between ice creams and frozen desserts, where later include only vegetable fats/oils instead of milk fat in formulation [12-53-78]. Similarly, in certain pockets of the country the plant-based milk substitute are mixed with bovine milk to manufacture milk products like paneer, cheeses, fermented milk and even traditional dairy products. Since such products are available at cheaper price, it adversely affect the market of dairy products[13-53-78].

3. Plant-based Milk

Plant-based milk alternatives are often marketed as nutritional replacements for bovine milk. Plant-based milk can be made from a wide variety of cereals, legumes, nuts, and seeds. The manufacturing process of various plant-based milks depends on the raw materials used [12-53-78]. There are two main methods for processing plant-based milk: wet or dry. The wet process involves soaking and grinding the raw material in large volumes of water for up to 12 hours [13-53-78]. The dry process involves milling the raw material into a flour or powder, which is then processed to separate the starch, protein, and fiber as desired, before being hydrated [13-53-78]. In the case of plant-based milk substitutes, starch gelatinization can occur when the product is heated, leading to a thicker, more viscous consistency. Therefore, in order to obtain milk like consistency various processing aids are employed, which not only increase the price of the product but also alters the natural status of the beverage [14-53-78]. For the preparation of few variants, enzymes are added to hydrolyze starches and reduce the viscosity, for example, in oat milk production. Enzymatic treatment is also required to maintain the non-dairy milk in the liquid state [12-53-78]. Additionally, various emulsifying agents such as alginates, gelatin, xanthan gum, gum Arabic, locust bean gum, and gellan gum have been explored for their use in plant-based milk substitutes to improve emulsion stability mainly seed or nut based extracts [12-53-78]. Plant-based milk substitutes lack certain key nutrients compared to milk, more particularly lactose and protein (Casein & whey proteins) and calcium [12-53-78]. This can affect the growth and activity of LAB starter, amylolytic LAB as well as poor proteolytic activity during fermentation. Beans and nuts which are utilized in preparation of plant based dairy alternatives may contain a number of anti-nutrients factors such as enzyme inhibitors, minerals chelators and even carcinogenic compounds [13-53-78]. Moreover, altered lipid compositions in "Vegan Milks" not only limit their shelf-life but also generate number of free radicals and free-radical mediated ROS which have implicated in degenerative processes in body. All non-milk plant base beverages (PBBS) have added sweetness, sugar, artificial flavors, artificial colors, thickeners, salt and preservatives (highest amount of thickeners is in soya beverage) [13-53-78]. Another serious issue that is affecting Indian dairy sector is rising incidences of adulteration, as these so called "plant-based milk" are mixed easily up to certain levels without being noticed by human taste senses [13-53-78].

4. Hemp seed milk

Hemp seed milk is made by homogenizing ground seeds in water (1.5 w/v), and the filtered milk, is generally heated for extended shelf life [13-78]. Commercial stable hemp seed milk production is challenging since hemp seed milk as an oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion is unstable and prone to flocculation, coalescence, and creaming [12-53-78]. This will result in a low-quality product with a short shelf life and lower consumer acceptance [13-78]. Therefore, exogenous emulsifiers and stabilizers are often used to improve the stability of emulsions to get stable hemp seed milk [13-78]. However, using these additives is not cost-effective because it raises production costs and has some health concerns, such as chronic inflammatory diseases, obesity-related diseases, and metabolic disorders [13-78]. Therefore, there is a pressing need to produce hemp seed milk free of added chemical substances [13-78]. Hemp protein has a low emulsifying capacity since its structure is compact and it has poor water solubility, low emulsion stability index, and water-holding capacity [13-78]. Further, hemp seed proteins have low heat stability and are affected and started to aggregate when exposed to heat treatment at 80°C or above for 10 min [13-78].

One of the multiple examples of functional food products are these containing microorganisms endogenous to the human gastrointestinal tract and exhibiting a positive effect on human health [10-78]. So far, the greatest part of probiotic products has been offered by fermented beverages made of animal milk. Currently, research is underway into other products that may be matrix for probiotic bacteria [10-78]. Consumers avoiding milk because of allergies or lactose intolerance, and consumers following a vegan diet can replace milk with other plant-based substitutes [13-78]. Today, coconut, almonds, hemp, and various cereals (e.g., oats, buckwheat, and rice) are also used to produce plant-based beverages [13-78]. A drawback of these products is however, their specific taste that does not suit to everyone [13-79]. A solution to this problem is offered by lactic acid fermentation, which imparts a characteristic, pleasant after-taste to these products and contributes to the improvement of the digestibility [13-78]. Numerous attempts have recently been undertaken to ferment vegan beverages serving as milk substitutes using various strains of probiotic bacteria, which was expected to additionally increase their health value [13-78]. However, most of the study results reported in literature concern the feasibility of producing fermented soybean milk [13-78]. This is related to the fact, that manufacture of high quality plant-based beverages containing probiotic bacteria poses a serious challenge [13-78]. The first ones were related to the stability of produced emulsions, whereas the latter ones to the survivability of probiotic bacteria during storage [13-78]. The production of hemp-based products has increased in recent years due to the confirmed nutritional value and low allergenicity of seeds of this plant [13-78].

5. Conclusion

The Agriculture Organization of the United States and the World Health Organization defined probiotics in 2001 as bacteria that, when given to a host at adequate levels, improve their health. Regarding probiotics, *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* are the two most frequently used genera. These bacteria are generally thought of as harmless due to their ability to survive in the body to cure and prevent diseases, unlike the usual pathogens. Along with that, these microorganisms have played a vital role in the process of fermenting milk and food preservation for many years. Hemp seed milk is one of the most important seed-based milk products; it is produced from industrial *Cannabis sativa* (hemp or fibre type). As previously said, demand for plant-based milk is increasing every day, but due to a lack of information and a generally unfavorable attitude toward discriminating between hemp and other cannabis types, the demand for hemp seed milk is insufficient and limited. The sources of plant-based milk, can be divided into five categories as cereal-based (oat milk, rice milk, corn milk, spelt milk), legume-based (soy milk, peanut milk, lupine milk, cowpea milk), nut-based (almond milk, coconut milk, hazelnut milk, pistachio milk, walnut milk, cashew milk), seed-based (sesame milk, flax milk, hemp seed milk, sunflower milk) and pseudo-cereal based (quinoa milk, teff milk, amaranth milk, buckwheat milk). The impact on the market will be significant as customers continue to seek more holistic solutions to wellness, thus propelling the demand for hemp milk as an ingredient for health-enhancing beverages. The production of protein powders from hemp milk is one of the most thrilling developments in the hemp milk industry. While plant-based protein powders made from peas, rice, and soy have been around for a long time, hemp-based protein powder is increasingly becoming popular due to its nutritional benefits and digestibility. Consumer preference for healthier and sustainable foods has been one of the most significant drivers in the growth of the hemp milk market. Improving awareness and knowledge while offering diverse gut-healthy foods in all strata of Indian society can increase the utilization of these foods and improve general health and prevent chronic diseases.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Kolkar KP, Malabadi RB, Chalannavar RK, Divakar MS, Swathi, Kamble AA, Karamchand KS, Castaño-Coronado KV, Munhoz ANR, Mammadova SS. Industrial *Cannabis sativa* (Fiber or Hemp): Hemp Cottonization-Advantages and Current Challenges. International Journal of Science and Research Archive. 2025; 14(03): 1233-1267.
- [2] Chalannavar RK, Malabadi RB, Divakar MS, Swathi, Komalakshi KV, Kamble AA Kishore S, Karamchand KS, Kolkar KP, Castaño-Coronado KV, Munhoz ANR. Industrial *Cannabis sativa* (Fiber or Hemp): Hemp made Leather. World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews. 2025 25(02): 2207-2218.
- [3] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H. Plant Based Leather Production-An update. World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences. 2025; 14(01): 031-059.
- [4] Kaminski KP, Hoeng J, Goffman F, Schlage WK, Latino D. Opportunities, Challenges, and Scientific Progress in Hemp Crops. Molecules. 2024; 20;29(10):2397. doi: 10.3390/molecules29102397.
- [5] Schumacher AGD, Pequito S, Pazour J. Industrial Hemp Fiber: A Sustainable and Economical Alternative to Cotton. Journal of Cleaner Production. 2020; DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122180.
- [6] Vasantha Rupasinghe HP, Davis A, Kumar SK, Beth Murray B, Zheljzkov VD. Industrial Hemp (*Cannabis sativa* subsp. *sativa*) as an Emerging Source for Value-Added Functional Food Ingredients and Nutraceuticals. Molecules. 2020; 25: 4078.
- [7] Andre CM, Hausman JF, Guerriero G. Cannabis sativa: The plant of the thousand and one molecules. Front. Plant Sci. 2016; 7:19.
- [8] Ceylan I, Alp NC, Aytac A. Sustainable 3D printing with alkali-treated hemp fiber-reinforced polycarbonate composites. Cellulose. 2024; 31:4477-4495. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-024-05904-x>.
- [9] Schmid L. Hemp vs. Cotton: 12 Reasons why Hemp is the Better Choice. Signature Products Magazine. 2022. July 1 (Hemp vs. Cotton: 12 Reasons why Hemp is the Better Choice (signature-products.com)).

- [10] Chalannavar RK, Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Divarkar MS, Swathi, Karamchand KS, Nandini N, Munhoz ANR. Probiotics: Health benefits-An update. World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences. 2025; 15(03): 2395-2403.
- [11] Chalannavar RK, Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Divarkar MS, Swathi, Karamchand KS, Nandini N, Munhoz ANR. Probiotic Yeasts-An Updated Review. Magna Scientia Advanced Biology and Pharmacy. 2025; 15(01): 49-59
- [12] Nissen L, Carlo ED, Gianotti A. Prebiotic potential of hemp blended drinks fermented by probiotics. Food Research International. 2020; 131: 109029, ISSN 0963-9969, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109029>.
- [13] Lee PR, Boo CX, Liu SQ. Fermentation of coconut water by probiotic strains *Lactobacillus acidophilus* L10 and *Lactobacillus casei* L26. Ann Microbio. 2013; 63, 1441–1450 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13213-013-0607-z>.
- [14] Nissen L, Demircan B, Taneyo-Saa DL, Gianotti A. Shift of Aromatic Profile in Probiotic Hemp Drink Formulations: A Metabolomic Approach. Microorganisms. 2019 Oct 29;7(11):509. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms7110509.
- [15] Liu Y, Fei Y, Li C, Cheng J, Xue F. Impact of Probiotic Fermentation on the Physicochemical Properties of Hemp Seed Protein Gels. Polymers. 2024; 16: 3032. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16213032>.
- [16] Nissen L, Demircan B, Taneyo-Saa DL, Gianotti A. Shift of Aromatic Profile in Probiotic Hemp Drink Formulations: A Metabolomic Approach. Microorganisms. 2019; 7L 509; doi:10.3390/microorganisms711050.
- [17] Patricio Rocha B, de Brito Lopes PL, Oliveira Morais da Silva M, Guimarães Gomes AC, Alonso Buriti FC, Menezes Florêncio I, Rolim Florentino E. Utilization of ripe coconut water in the development of probiotic gelatin. Peer J. 2024 Jun 28;12:e17502. doi: 10.7717/peerj.17502.
- [18] Segura-Badilla O, Lazcano-Hernández M, Kammar-García A, Vera-López O, Aguilar-Alonso P, Ramírez-Calixto J, Navarro-Cruz AR. Use of coconut water (*Cocos nucifera* L) for the development of a symbiotic functional drink. Heliyon. 2020 Mar 28;6(3):e03653. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03653.
- [19] Zang J, Yan B, Hu H, Liu Z, Tang D, Liu Y, Chen J, Tu Y, Yin, Z. The current advances, challenges, and future trends of plant-based yogurt. Trends Food Sci. Technol. 2024; 149: 104531.
- [20] Zhou Y, Xu Y, Song S, Zhan S, Li X, Wang H, Zhu Z, Yan L, Peng Y, Xie C. Effect of Different Probiotic Fermentations on the Quality of Plant-Based Hempseed Fermented Milk. Foods. 2024; 13: 4076. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods1324407>
- [21] Callaway JC. Hempseed as a nutritional resource: An overview. Euphytica. 2024, 140, 65–72.
- [22] House JD, Neufeld J, Leson G. Evaluating the quality of protein from hemp seed (*Cannabis sativa* L.) products through the use of the protein digestibility-corrected amino acid score method. J. Agric. Food Chem. 2010; 58: 11801–11807.
- [23] Wang QL, Xiong YL. Processing, Nutrition, and Functionality of Hempseed Protein: A Review. Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf. 2019; 18: 936–952.
- [24] Grasso N, Alonso-Miravalles L, O'Mahony JA. Composition, Physicochemical and Sensorial Properties of Commercial Plant-Based Yogurts. Foods. 2020; 9: 252.
- [25] Mishra BK, Hati S, Das S, Prajapati JB. Biofunctional Attributes and Storage Study of Soy Milk Fermented by *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* and *Lactobacillus helveticus*. Food Technol. Biotechnol. 2019; 57:399–407.
- [26] Keshika P, Sivamaruthi BS, Chaiyasut C. A review on the functional properties of fermented soymilk. Food Sci. Technol. 2022; 42: e10721.
- [27] Shori AB, Aljohani GS, Al-zahrani AJ, Al-sulbi OS, Baba AS. Viability of probiotics and antioxidant activity of cashew milk-based yogurt fermented with selected strains of probiotic *Lactobacillus* spp. LWT-Food Sci. Technol. 2022; 153: 112482.
- [28] Supavititpatana P, Wirjantoro TI, Apichartsrangkoon A, Raviyan P. Addition of gelatin enhanced gelation of corn-milk yogurt. Food Chem. 2008; 106: 211–216.
- [29] Dumas AA, Lapointe A, Dugrenier M, Provencher V, Lamarche B, Desroches S. A systematic review of the effect of yogurt consumption on chronic diseases risk markers in adults. Eur. J. Nutr. 2017; 56:1375–1392.
- [30] Nakashima Y, Yamamoto N, Tsukioka R, Sugawa H, Ohshima R, Aoki K, Hibi T, Onuki K, Fukuchi Y, Yasuda S et al. In vitro evaluation of the anti-diabetic potential of soymilk yogurt and identification of inhibitory compounds on the formation of advanced glycation end-products. Food Biosci. 2022; 50: 102051.

- [31] Zhang XL, Wu YF, Wang YS, Wang XZ, Piao CH, Liu JM, Liu YL, Wang YH. The protective effects of probiotic fermented soymilk on high-fat diet-induced hyperlipidemia and liver injury. *J. Funct. Foods*. 2017; 30: 220–22.
- [32] Pojić M, Mišan A, Sakač M, Dapčević Hadnadev T, Šarić B, Milovanović I, Hadna dev M. Characterization of byproducts originating from hemp oil processing. *J. Agric. Food Chem*. 2014; 62: 12436–12442.
- [33] Aiello G, Lammi C, Boschini G, Zanoni C, Arnoldi A. Exploration of Potentially Bioactive Peptides Generated from the Enzymatic Hydrolysis of Hempseed Proteins. *J. Agric. Food Chem*. 2017; 65: 10174–10184.
- [34] Thakur A, Morya S, Alsulami T, Charles Brennan C, Nayik GA. Optimization of Hemp Seed Milk Production Using Response Surface Methodology: Enhancing Nutritional Quality and Reducing Anti-nutrients. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*. 2024; 1-13. Volume 2024, Article ID 6015666, 13 pages <https://doi.org/10.1155/jfpp/6015666>.
- [35] Karabulut G, Nemzer BV, Feng H. γ -Aminobutyric Acid (GABA)-enriched Hemp Milk by Solid-state Co-fermentation and Germination Bioprocesses. *Plant Foods Hum Nutr*. 2024; 79, 322–329.
- [36] Hemp Milk Market Size, Demand, Trends & Forecast 2025-2035 (futuremarketinsights.com).
- [37] Szparaga A, Tabor S, Kocira S, Czerwinska E, Kubon M, Płóciennik B, and Findura P. Survivability of Probiotic Bacteria in Model Systems of Non-Fermented and Fermented Coconut and Hemp Milks. *Sustainability*. 2019; 11(21): 6093; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11216093>.
- [38] Besir A, Awad N, Mortas M, Yazici1 F. A Plant-Based Milk Type: Hemp Seed Milk. *Akademik Gıda*. 2022; 20(2): 170-181, DOI: 10.24323/akademik-gida.1149875.
- [39] Han CE, Ewe JA, Kuan CS, Yeo SK. Growth characteristic of probiotic in fermented coconut milk and the antibacterial properties against *Streptococcus pyogenes*. *J Food Sci Technol*. 2022; Sep;59(9):3379-3386. doi: 10.1007/s13197-021-05321-z.
- [40] Shetty SM, Shah DS, Goyal G, Kathuria NS, Abraham J, Bhatia V. A study to find the status of probiotics in New Delhi, India and review of strains of bacteria used as probiotics. *J Int Soc Prev Community Dent*. 2014 Nov;4(Suppl 1):S18-22. doi: 10.4103/2231-0762.144570.
- [41] Raja BR, Arunachalam KD. Market potential for probiotic nutritional supplements in India. *African Journal of Business Management*. 2011; 5(14): 5418-5423.
- [42] Kumar M, Goyal R, Khandal H, Khilwani B, Gupta S, Lomash H, Ghosh M, and 1 Ganguli A. PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDES OF INDIAN CONSUMERS TO PROBIOTIC FOODS. *CURRENT TOPICS IN NUTRACEUTICAL RESEARCH*. 2010; 8: 4: XX-XX.
- [43] Shireen A, Aneesh M. Knowledge and consumption of probiotics and prebiotics in India: a narrative review. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*. 2021 Oct;8(10):5119-5126.
- [44] Kerry GR, Patra JK, Gouda S, Park Y, Shin HS, Das G. Benefaction of probiotics for human health: A review. *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis*. 2018;26(3):927-39.
- [45] Pandey KR, Naik SR, Vakil BV. Probiotics, prebiotics and synbiotics- a review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2015;52(12):7577-87.
- [46] Raza A, Kalaivani K, Ramachandran P. Nutrition transition in India: Overview of dietary intake and nutrition status (2000–Present). *Advances in Food Security and Sustainability*. 2019;4:175-91.
- [47] Bhupathiraju K, Krishnaraju AV, Sengupta K, Golakoti T, Akolkar SK, Datla P. Regulations on nutraceuticals, functional foods, and dietary supplements in India. *Nutraceutical and Functional Food Regulations in the United States and around the World*. 2019;445-64.
- [48] Arora M, Kaur N, Arora M, Bansal P. Critical Review on Food Safety Standard Regulations: A Real Scrutinizing Authority or a Misleading Player for Probiotic Products. *Applied Clinical Research, Clinical Trials and Regulatory Affairs*. 2018;6(2):71-85.
- [49] Shireen A. Knowledge, Consumption and Perception of Probiotics and Prebiotics among Indian Adults. 2021. Unpublished Masters Dissertation. Mount Carmel College, Autonomous, India.
- [50] Kumar SR, Kanmani P, Yuvaraj N, Paari KA, Pattukumar V, Arul V. Traditional Indian fermented foods: A rich source of lactic acid bacteria. *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition*. 2013;64(4):415-28.
- [51] Chaudhary A, Sharma DK, Arora A. Prospects of Indian traditional fermented food as functional foods. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. 2018;88(10):1496-501.

- [52] Panesar PS, Bali V, Kumari S, Neha Babbar Brar SK, Dhillon GS, Soccol CR. Biotransformation of Waste Biomass into High Value Biochemicals. 2014;9781461480:1-504.
- [53] Samanta AK, Kolte AP, Senani S, Sridhar M, Jayapal N. Prebiotics in ancient Indian diets. *Current Science*. 2011;101(1):43-6.
- [54] Thammarutwasik P, Hongpattarakere T, Chantachum S, Kijroongrojana K, Itharat A, Reanmongkol W, Tewtrakul S, Ooraikul B. Prebiotics – A Review. *Songklanakarinn Journal of Science*. 2009;31(4):401- 8.
- [55] Lakshmy G, Seetha Devi B, Ramesh B. The blooming prospects of probiotic products in India. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*. 2018;7(4):253-8.
- [56] Kumar M, Goyal R, Khandal H, Khilwani A, Gupta S, Lomash H et al. Perception and attitudes of Indian consumers to probiotic foods. *International Journal of Probiotics and Prebiotics* 2010;5(4):217-20.
- [57] Arora, Prabha K. Consumer awareness and willingness to purchase probiotic food and beverage products : a study of Sonapat district, Haryana awareness. *British Food Journal*. 2020.
- [58] Das J, Raju R, Sirohi S, Chandel BS, Raju PN, Meena BS. Consumption pattern of fermented probiotic dairy Products in metropolitan Delhi. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2019;8(1):45-9.
- [59] Sahib KP, Rakesh KP, Pal SS, Apoorva S, Nidhi G. Awareness and knowledge of people towards probiotics products in Punjab region. *International Journal of Applied Biology and Pharmaceutical Technology* 2016;1:154-61.
- [60] Al-Nabulsi AA, Obiedat B, Ali R, Osaili TM, Bawadi H, Abushelaibi A et al. Knowledge of probiotics and factors affecting their consumption by Jordanian College students. *International Journal of Probiotics and Prebiotics*. 2014;9(3):77-86.
- [61] Gnanamkonda V, Prasad S. Consumer awareness and consumption pattern of probiotic & sugar free ice creams in Hyderabad & Secunderabad. *ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*. 2014;4(4):162-71.
- [62] Chin-Lee B, Curry WJ, Fetterman J, Graybill MA, Karpa K. Patient experience and use of probiotics in community-based health care settings. *Patient Preference and Adherence*. 2014;8:1513-20.
- [63] Khalesi S, Vandelanotte C, Thwaite T, Russell AMT, Dawson D, Williams SL. Awareness and Attitudes of Gut Health, Probiotics and Prebiotics in Australian Adults. *Journal of Dietary Supplements*. 2021;18(4):418-32.
- [64] Yilmaz-ersan L, Ozcan T, Akpınar-bayizit A. Food Science and Human Wellness Assessment of sociodemographic factors, health status and the knowledge on probiotic dairy products. *Food Science and Human Wellness*. 2020;9(3):272-9.
- [65] Hardia S. Designing of economical media for the growth of probiotics by using waste materials. *Devi Ahiliya Vishwavidyalaya, Indore*. 2012. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/238069>. Accessed on 20 July 2021.
- [66] Panghal A, Janghu S, Virkar K, Gat Y, Kumar V, Chhikara N. Potential non-dairy probiotic products – A healthy approach. *Food Bioscience*. 2018;21:80-9. 39. Ranadheera CS, Vidanarachchi JK, Rocha RS, Cruz AG, Ajlouni S. Probiotic Delivery through Fermentation: Dairy vs. Non-Dairy Beverages. *Fermentation*. 2017;1-17.
- [67] Lakshmy G, Seetha Devi B, Ramesh B. The Blooming Prospects of Probiotic Products in India. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE) ISSN: 2277-3878 (Online)*. 2019; 7: 4s2, 253-258.
- [68] Hajela N, Nair GB, Ramakrishna BS, Ganguly NK. Probiotic foods: can their increasing use in India ameliorate the burden of chronic lifestyle disorders? *Indian J. Med Res*. 2014 Jan;139(1):19-26.
- [69] Gajbe J, Deshmukh V, Deshpande R, Jagtap R, Pawar T. MARKET ANALYSIS OF MOST SELLING PROBIOTIC-VIBACT & VIBACT DS, *International Journal of Research in Commerce and Management Studies (IJRCMS)*. 2025; 7 (3): 231-245 Article No. 403 Sub Id 726.
- [70] Probiotics Market Analysis Report 2025 with Analyst (globenewswire.com).
- [71] Rathore M, Sharma K. PROBIOTICS AND THEIR INDIAN AND GLOBAL VALUE: A REVIEW. *WORLD JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL AND MEDICAL RESEARCH. (wjpmr)*. 2017;3(8): 43-54.
- [72] India Probiotics Market Size, Share & Trends | Report 2033 (imarcgroup.com)
- [73] India's probiotics market doubles in five years, hits Rs. 2,070 crore (US\$ 242 million) in 2025 | IBEF.
- [74] India Probiotic Market Size, Share and Forecast 2030F | TechSci Research

- [75] Bodke H, Jogdand S. Role of Probiotics in Human Health. *Cureus*. 2022 Nov 9;14(11):e31313. doi: 10.7759/cureus.31313.
- [76] Kechagia M, Basoulis D, Konstantopoulou S, Dimitriadi D, Gyftopoulou K, Skarmoutsou N, Fakiri EM. Health benefits of probiotics: a review. *ISRN Nutr*. 2013 Jan 2;2013:481651. doi: 10.5402/2013/481651.
- [77] Sarita B, Samadhan D, Hassan MZ and Kovaleva EG. A comprehensive review of probiotics and human health-current prospective and applications. *Front. Microbiol*. 2025; 15:1487641. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2024.1487641.
- [78] Sulaimany S, Farahmandi K, Mafakheri A. Computational prediction of new therapeutic effects of probiotics. *Sci Rep*. 2024; 14: 11932 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-62796-4>.
- [79] Singhal S, Baker RD, Baker SS. A comparison of the nutritional value of cow's milk and nondairy beverages. *J. Ped. Gastroenterol. Nutr*. 2017; 64: 799–805.
- [80] Kolkar KP, Annapurna S, Malabadi RB, Jayashree BK, Chalannavar RK, Divakar MS, Karamchand KS, Baijnath H. Indian probiotic food: Gut health management: An updated review. *World Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2025; 23(01): 431-447.
- [81] Jayashree KB, Chalannavar RK, Nandini N, Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Divarkar MS. Yeast probiotics fermented food products: Gut microbiome and Women health. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2025; 27(01):1209-1230.
- [82] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. *Cannabis sativa*: Ethnobotany and Phytochemistry. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5(2): 3990-3998.
- [83] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. *Cannabis sativa*: Industrial hemp (fiber type)- An *Ayurvedic* traditional herbal medicine. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review* 2023; 5 (2): 4040-4046.
- [84] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Achary M, Chalannavar RK. *Cannabis sativa*: Medicinal plant with 1000 Molecules of Pharmaceutical Interest. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5(2): 3999-4005.
- [85] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. Medical *Cannabis sativa* (Marijuana or Drug type); The story of discovery of Δ 9-Tetrahydrocannabinol (THC). *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5 (3):4134-4143.
- [86] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. Δ 9-Tetrahydrocannabinol (THC): The major Psychoactive Component is of Botanical origin. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5(3): 4177-4184.
- [87] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Lavanya L, Abdi G. *Cannabis sativa*: Botany, Cross Pollination and Plant Breeding Problems. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8 (4): 174-190.
- [88] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. *Cannabis sativa*: Industrial Hemp (fibre-type)- An emerging opportunity for India. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovations (IJRSI)*. 2023; X (3):01-9.
- [89] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. Industrial *Cannabis sativa* (Hemp fiber type): Hempcrete-A plant based eco-friendly building construction material. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Sciences (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8(3): 67-78.
- [90] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Lavanya L, Abdi G. *Cannabis sativa*: The difference between Δ 8-THC and Δ 9-Tetrahydrocannabinol (THC). *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5(4): 4315-4318.
- [91] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Lavanya L, Abdi G. Hemp Helps Human Health: Role of phytocannabinoids. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5 (4): 4340-4349.
- [92] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Lavanya L, Abdi G, Baijnath H. Cannabis products contamination problem: A major quality issue. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023;5(4): 4402-4405.
- [93] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Lavanya L, Abdi G. Medical *Cannabis sativa* (Marijuana or drug type): Psychoactive molecule, Δ 9-Tetrahydrocannabinol (Δ 9-THC). *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science*. 2023; 8(4): 236-249.

- [94] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Mondal M, Lavanya L, Abdi G, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Release of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) affecting air quality. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8(5): 23-35.
- [95] **Malabadi RB**, Nethravathi TL, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Mudigoudra BS, Lavanya L, Abdi G, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Applications of Artificial Intelligence and Plant Tissue Culture for Micropropagation. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8(6): 117-142.
- [96] Malabadi RB, Nethravathi TL, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Mudigoudra BS, Abdi G, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Applications of Artificial intelligence (AI) in Cannabis industries: In Vitro plant tissue culture. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8 (7): 21-40. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*. 2023; 10(02): 860–873.
- [97] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Brindha C, Chalannavar RK, Abdi G, Baijnath H, Munhoz ANR, Mudigoudra BS. *Cannabis sativa*: Autoflowering and Hybrid Strains. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5(7): 4874-4877.
- [98] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Munhoz ANR, Abdi G, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Dioecious into Monoecious Plants influencing Sex Determination. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8(7): 82-91.
- [99] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Difference between Medical Cannabis (marijuana or drug) and Industrial hemp. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2023; 24(03):377–81.
- [100] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Abdi G, Munhoz ANR, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Dengue viral disease-Vector control measures. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*. 2023; 5(8): 5013-5016.
- [101] Malabadi RB, Nethravathi TL, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Mudigoudra BS, Abdi G, Munhoz ANR, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: One-Plant-One-Medicine for many diseases-Therapeutic Applications. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8(8): 132-174.
- [102] Malabadi RB, Nethravathi TL, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Mudigoudra BS, Abdi G, Munhoz ANR, Baijnath H. Fungal Infection Diseases- Nightmare for Cannabis Industries: Artificial Intelligence Applications *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*. 2023; 8(8):111-131.
- [103] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Acharya M, Mudigoudra BS. *Cannabis sativa*: 2023-Outbreak and Re-emergence of Nipah virus (NiV) in India: Role of Hemp oil. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2023; 25(01):063–077.
- [104] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Acharya M, Mudigoudra BS. *Industrial Cannabis sativa*: Hemp-Biochar-Applications and Disadvantages. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2023; 20(01): 371–383.
- [105] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Vassanthini R, Mudigoudra BS. *Industrial Cannabis sativa*: Hemp plastic-Updates. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2023; 20 (01): 715-725.
- [106] **Malabadi RB**, Sadiya MR, Kolkar KP, Lavanya L, Chalannavar RK. Quantification of THC levels in different varieties of *Cannabis sativa*. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*. 2023; 10(02): 860–873.
- [107] Malabadi RB, Sadiya MR, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. Biodiesel production via transesterification reaction. *Open Access Research Journal of Science and Technology*. 2023; 09(02): 010–021.
- [108] Malabadi RB, Sadiya MR, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. Biodiesel production: An updated review of evidence. *International Journal of Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences Archive*. 2023; 06(02): 110–133.
- [109] **Malabadi RB**, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. *Industrial Cannabis sativa*: Hemp oil for biodiesel production. *Magna Scientia Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2023; 09(02): 022–035.
- [110] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK. *Industrial Cannabis sativa*: Role of hemp (fiber type) in textile industries. *World Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2023; 16(02): 001–014.
- [111] Malabadi RB, Mammadova SS, Kolkar KP, Sadiya MR, Chalannavar RK, Castaño Coronado KV. *Cannabis sativa*: A therapeutic medicinal plant-global marketing updates. *World Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2024; 17(02):170–183.
- [112] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Sadiya MR, Veena Sharada B, Mammadova SS, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H, Nalini S, Nandini S, Munhoz ANR. Triple Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC): *Cannabis sativa*-Role of Phytocannabinoids. *World Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2024; 17(03): 140–179.

- [113] Malabadi RB, Sadiya MR, Kolkar KP, Mammadova SS, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H. Role of Plant derived-medicine for controlling Cancer. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*. 2024; 11(01): 2502–2539.
- [114] Malabadi RB, Sadiya MR, Kolkar KP, Mammadova SS, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H, Lavanya L, Munhoz ANR. Triple Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC): Signaling pathways-Role of plant-based inhibitors. *Open Access Research Journal of Biology and Pharmacy*, 2024; 10(02), 028–071.
- [115] Fernando de C, Lambert C, Barbosa Filh, EV, Castaño Coronado KV, Malabadi RB. Exploring the potentialities of industrial hemp for sustainable rural development. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2024; 18(01): 305–320.
- [116] Malabadi RB, Sadiya MR, Prathima TC, Kolkar KP, Mammadova SS, Chalannavar RK. *Cannabis sativa*: Cervical cancer treatment- Role of phytocannabinoids-A story of concern. *World Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2024; 17(02): 253–296.
- [117] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Monoecious species and Hermaphroditism: Feminized seed production- A breeding effort. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2024; 20(03): 169-183.
- [118] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Extraction Methods for Phytocannabinoids -An Update. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2024; 20(03): 018–058.
- [119] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Baijnath H. *Cannabis sativa*: Polyploidization-Triploid and Tetraploid Production. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*. 2024; 20(03), 567-587.
- [120] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Castaño Coronado KV, Chalannavar RK. *Cannabis sativa*: Quality control testing measures and guidelines: An update. *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*. 2025;14(01): 110-129.
- [121] Mariz J, Guise C, Silva TL, Rodrigues L, Silva CJ. Hemp: From Field to Fiber—A Review. *Textiles*. 2024; 4: 165–182. <https://doi.org/10.3390/textiles4020011>.
- [122] **Malabadi RB**, Chalannavar RK, Divakar MS, Swathi, Komalakshi KV, Kamble AA, Karamchand KS, Kolkar KP, Nethravathi TL, Castaño- Coronado KV, Munhoz ANR. Industrial *Cannabis sativa* (Fiber or Hemp): 3D printing-hempcrete-A sustainable building material. *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*. 2025;14(02): 253-282.
- [123] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Chalannavar RK, Munhoz ANR. *In vitro* Anther culture and Production of Haploids in *Cannabis sativa*. *Open Access Research Journal of Science and Technology*. 2025; 13(01): 001-020. (<https://doi.org/10.53022/oarjst.2025.13.1.0150>).